

Performance Model Development Organization And Service Image Integrate System Service Leadership And Innovation Society Organization To Face Global

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 13, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Care leadership, Organizational Innovation, Service Image, Development Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5842426</p>	<p><i>A change in attitudes and behavior phenomenon of global society is very drastic, sudden, continuous and unexpected make the service system also become a part of the change, both seen in public and business organizations. Therefore a public organization in order to be at the forefront as a community service organization. Thus, as a people's service organization that begins at the level of its leader with its capabilities, with high innovation, the communication style carried out is always oriented towards global organizational performance, so that the service image becomes part of the global community. However, its implementation is currently the main problem, from old habits to new habits, namely a fast, precise, safe and pleasant service. Indeed, currently some public organizations or businesses internally cannot say that the service theory results in loyal and loyal consumers for the service image they get. This study aims to examine how variables such as service leadership, organizational innovation, organizational performance & service image affect consumers located in developing countries. The findings from the analysis of the structural equation model tested by end users consisting of 144 (one hundred and forty four) selected employees in Eastern Indonesia prove that the application of service theory in service leadership, organizational innovation and organizational performance & service image to consumers. This research underlies the importance of a high-quality leader with a reliable leadership style so as to improve performance to satisfy consumers in various parts of the world with a deep service image in the eyes of consumers, so that public organizations can contribute to the current era of global competition.</i></p>

Introduction

The problem of symptoms of the low level of services of public organization & business organization in the last decade on the performance of the organization and the service image, becoming more prominent, Masip, erratic and possibly disturbing the good order of practical and also scientific studies in various countries, also in Indonesia with various perceptions of each. Studies on service leadership, innovation capabilities and organizational performance & service image to consumers will provide solutions such as:

i) The study tries to develop not only the characteristics of growing organizations, but also leadership factors, organizational design culture and information sharing. Forter & Sidharta (Foster & Sidharta, 2019) in Robbins & Coulter (Robbins & Coulter, 2010). ii). Servant Leadership has reversed the situation from old public administration to New public service, not only public organizations but also business organizations are basically very consent so that servant leaders can become the mainstay of loyal consumers for certain products. It is characterized by service that goes beyond the leader's own interests. Or is the first person to become a servant, so that he becomes an example and role model for those around him. Robbins & Judge (Robbins & Judge, 2015), Greenleaf (Greenleaf, 1999), Goh & Zhen-Jie (Goh & Zhen-Jie, 2014), Winston & Ryan (Winston & Ryan, 2008), Harwiki (Harwiki, 2013) . iii) The innovation ability of a company becomes an important factor, so that it becomes a competitive advantage, which in turn will increase satisfaction and service image. Innovation acceptance & implementation of new ideas, processes or products. It can also be part of systems, policies and programs, new processes, new marketing management that are more effective and efficient. Nemati (Nemati et al., 2010). iv) Communication style is an important part of organizational development efforts. The development of transmission and reception of information at the subsystem level will cause ambiguity and complexities about norms and roles to be resolved properly and interpersonal trust can be built which will ultimately foster a sense of openness to each other. Schmuck (Schmuck, 1977), Sarwani (Sarwani, 2016), Smeltzer et al (Smeltzer et al., 1991) in Sarwani (Sarwani, 2016), Rogers & Agarwala-Rogers (Rogers & Agarwala-Rogers, 1976), Liliweri (Liliweri, 2010), Dienovyna et al (Dienovyna et al., 2015). V) Service image, company image and company credibility are a combination picture of the company's image as a whole. By

creating a consistent image of the organization, integrated through advertising, logos or symbols, management behavior and positive employee attitudes. (responsive, ethical, caring for the environment and trusted social issues.). Chang & Lee (Chang & Lee, 2007), Tjiptono (Tjiptono, 2008), Wijaya (Wijaya, 2011).

Evaluation of several things that resulted about the importance of steps and can develop service leadership, organizational innovation, organizational performance & service image (i) The world of work today has changed both groups or organizations and even state institutions. The key word is in adapting to the advancement of the times, especially in the field of organization to transform into a learning organization. Duha (Duha, 2018), Robbins & Judge (Robbins & Judge, 2015), Al Badi (Al Badi, 2019). (ii). The characteristics of service leadership should be more on empathetic listening, multiplying, examining services and actively developing the potential of their subordinates, awareness, conceptualization, commitment to human growth and community building. Greenleaf (Greenleaf, 1999), Goh & Zhen-Jie (Goh & Zhen-Jie, 2014).

(iii) In essence, innovation is doing something new and has added value (value added), besides that innovation is related to the development of new production methods and the establishment of a new management system. Crossan & Apaydin, 2010) (Crossan & Apaydin, 2010), But in reality how difficult and not easy to make changes or differences. Some subtle and open rejection of new methods and systems which of course require time for change.

(iv) Leadership communication in the organization can be illustrated in specific ways in building innovation in the organization. With a change in new ways with new expectations, the routine of organizational life, every communication that is spoken, conveys the meaning as well as what is written. Liliweri (Liliweri, 2010). Good communication should be able to improve good relations between co-workers, but not infrequently a small problem becomes a serious problem due to miscommunication, confusion due to different backgrounds and or arrogance of power.

(v) There is a view that the factors forming the service image come from the perception of the service as a physical entity and their behavior, including the company name, management philosophy, company reputation or credibility, service image or attitude shown by the company and so on. Walters (Walters, 1978), Nguyen & Leblanc (Nguyen & Leblanc, 2001). Some agencies/companies are still found to have an unfavorable image and a negative image in the eyes of customers as a result of the company's image management system created from an inconsistent, not yet integrated organization from various logos, advertisements, symbols, management behavior and employee alerts that tend to be negative/responsive. , ethical concern for the environment and social issues, distrust of company policies that carry out corporate social responsibility programs and logo changes. Tjiptono (Tjiptono, 2008).

Thus, it will be the main turning point that researchers carry out and develop in Indonesia. Furthermore, whether the theory of developing service leadership, innovation ability and organizational performance & service image according to the initial theory can be applied or can follow the progress achieved by more developed countries. This research is to provide a solution for how service leadership, innovation capabilities and organizational performance & service image contribute positively to business and public organizations in Indonesia.

2. Methodology

The target population of this study were 144 (one hundred and forty four) respondents, employees of the Banjarbaru City Communications and Information Technology, Tabalong Communications and Information Technology and Ex. Kominfo/Transportation Office of Tabalong Regency). Data were collected through a questionnaire during the period May 2020 to July 2020. By using the Structural Equational Model (SEM), which requires the number of sample sizes to be five to ten times the number of observations for each parameter Ferdinand (Ferdinand, 2006). The relationship between the constructions is described in the theoretical framework. A five-point Likert-type scale (1-strongly disagree: to strongly agree) was applied throughout the questionnaire. Factor loading is used to evaluate discriminant validity where only items with factor loading exceeding 0.50 will remain in the model (Ferdinand, 2006).

2.2 Identification of Research Variables

Organizational performance as an endogenous construct is measured by four dimensions: the financial sector is the central part of performance (OR01), fulfillment of customer desires (ORO2), service improvement and change (ORO3), easy, fast and convenient service (ORO4). Adapted from the work, Dempsey et al (Dempsey et al., 1997) and Service image with three dimensions: customer impressions of the organization's products are good and bad (SR01), customer trust is established in their minds for product satisfaction and loyalty (SR02), the existence of customer perception attitudes that make the service image good or vice versa (SR03), adapted from Kanaidi (Kanaidi, 2010). On the other hand, exogenous variables. Servant leadership is assessed by family leadership (SE01), the era of empowerment requires outstanding employees (SE02), the humility of an employee/leader (SE03), the task carried is trust (SE04) adapted from Dennis & Bocarnea (Dennis & Bocarnea, 2005). Organizational innovation is judged by new ideas for convenience, accuracy, convenience (IN01), creativity and responsiveness (IN02), new products and services (IN03), new services for handling a new program (SE04) adapted from the work of Calantane et al. (Calantane et al., 2002).

Description:

—→ Affects Z1 and Z2

Figure: 1: Conceptual framework on research variables affect Z1 and Z2

Reliability testing is used to determine the consistency of research measuring instruments, so that the measuring instrument is reliable if used more than 1 time. Test reliability and validity by calculating the results of regression weights, the AVE value has a value exceeding loading 0.5 and the CR value having 0.7, so that if it exceeds the values 0.5 and 0.7 which means that all variables have met the validity and reliability. . The normality test was carried out using a critical ratio value of ± 2.58 at a significance level of 0.01% (Ghozali, 2004) and that means the normality assumption is met and is feasible for further use. Research data is said to have outliers if the values of p1 and p2 are less than 5% and data containing outliers will be able to affect the normality of a data.

The existence of multicollinearity and singularity can be known through the value of the covariance matrix which is really small or close to zero. The confirmatory factor analysis test for these variables shows a collision of variables with a value of 0.05 means that these variables are significant in contributing to form the latent variable. Modification of the model is carried out according to software modification suggestions (modification indices), namely connecting several constructs with covariance lines so that there is a relationship between constructs. If the Good of Fit (GOF) Index as a result of the Cut Off Value of the Modified Research Model does not meet the GOF, the model must be modified so that all indices meet the specified criteria.

Hypothesis testing was carried out by observing the CR and Sig values of the studied variables based on the maximum likelihood estimates by looking at the regression weights table, which was said to have a significant effect if the CR variable value was 1.96 and probability <0.001 . Correlation test to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. . Meanwhile, to find out the magnitude of the effect caused by the variable on other variables, how much is its contribution, an effect test is carried out.

For scoring the answers to the questionnaire using a Likert scale. (Sugiyono, 2005), the Likert scale is used to measure attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. With the help of observing the values of CR and Sig Variables studied based on the maximum likelihood estimates by looking at the regression weights, eight hypotheses will be tested. - Learning orientation is negatively related to organizational performance - Learning orientation is negatively related to service image - Servant leadership is negatively related to service image. - Servant leadership is negatively related to organizational performance. - Innovation ability is negatively related to organizational performance. - Innovation ability is positively related to service image. - Communication style is positively related to organizational performance - Communication style is negatively related to service image.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1 Overview of Respondents

Based on the results of data collection in the field, through collecting answers obtained from 144 selected respondents, it proves that the implementation of servant leadership, Innovation ability in terms of organizational performance and service image makes an insignificant impact and tends to be positive on organizational performance and Service image leads to unsatisfactory organizational performance and maximum service image.

3.2 Construct Validity and Reliability Test

Validity test by calculating AVE and CR where AVE is 0.5, then the construct is said to be valid and the CR value is 0.7, then it is said to be reliable as the research results. According to the criteria of Guilford (Guilford, 1950) in Widodo (Widodo, 2006) that the reliability coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, the closer to 1, the more reliable the instrument is. Meanwhile, according to Nugroho (Nugroho, 2000) a variable is said to be good if it has Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.60 . in exploratory research, the reliability between 0.5-0.6 is acceptable. (Nunnally, 1994).

3.3 Normality Test .

The normality test was carried out using a critical ratio value of ± 2.58 at a significance level of 0.01% (Ghozali, 2004). The results of the normality and linearity test showed that all indicators had a cr value not exceeding 2.58 so that the research data were met. Meanwhile, research data is said to have outliers if the values of p1 and p2 are less than 5% and data containing outliers will be able to affect the normality of a data. From the results of the outlier test on the research data, it was not found that p1 and p2 had outlier values <0.05 . To obtain normal research data, all data containing outliers must be removed for further SEM analysis. The results of the SEM analysis were not found whose values were more than > 0.05 , so the research results were said to be normal.

3.4 Structural Equation Modeling

An index model that still does not meet the GOP, so it is modified to meet the criteria. Modification of the model is to connect several constructs with covariance lines so that there is a relationship between constructs, so that according to the criteria for Goodness Of Fit, the following is required:

From the table below displays the goodness index of fit. Post-evaluation it was found that all goodness of fit tests showed good results and that the model was in accordance with the data. Solomon et al (Solomon et al., 1992). Thus, according to theory and supported by facts, it means that the model is the best to explain the relationship between variables.

3.5 Hypothesis Testing

The effect test was carried out by observing the CR and Sig values of the variables studied based on the maximum likelihood estimates by looking at the regression weights table, which was said to have a significant effect if the variable CR value was 1.96 and the probability was < 0.000 . As the following table:

Correlation test was conducted to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. In this study, there were 9 relationships between variables that were correlated with each other. (Attachment). Then the total effect test is carried out with the results according to the following table:

Table. Test Total Effects

		Servant Leadership	Innovation Ability	
Organizational Performance		0,404	0,211	
Service Image		0.321	0.472	

Based on the results of the total effect test above, it can be seen that the Innovation Ability variable is the variable with the largest contribution in influencing the service Image (0.472) and Organizational performance (0.404) variables.

4. Discussion

(i) The influence of service leadership factor with four dimensions is family leadership, achievement in the era of empowerment, humble leader and duty is trust. Service leadership has no significant effect, which means that the hypothesis is not accepted on the service image. This means that the service image is not influenced by the dimensions of service leadership, in other words changes to the service image are not caused by service leadership regarding these four dimensions. This is inconsistent with Rorimpandey's research (Rorimpandey, 2013). Gani (Gani, 2020). that transformational leadership has a positive effect on performance. This is not in accordance with Wahyuni's research (Wahyuni, 2021). Ni'Am et al (Ni'Am et al., 2021). Sholikhah (Sholikhah, 2021), Noor et al (Noor et al., 2018). Setyawati et al (Setyawati et al., 2018). Research that service leadership has an effect on service image. Dinata et al (Dinata et al., 2018). In contrast to the results of research on positive leadership style on job satisfaction. Also along with research that organizational culture leadership is less conducive due to the administrative style head of the room. Noor et al (Noor et al., 2018).

(ii) Service leadership factors in terms of dimensions assessed are compassion, empowerment, humility and trust. This is in accordance with the research of Marjaya & Pasaribu (Marjaya & Pasaribu, 2019) that leadership has an insignificant negative effect on employee performance. This research does not coincide with research that leadership and high service quality will result in competitiveness, this indicates that the company's performance is higher. Eka (Eka, 2017). This research does not coincide with research conducted that leadership has a positive effect on performance. Hasibuan (Hasibuan, 2018). This is not in accordance with Wahyuni's research (Wahyuni, 2021).

(iii) Variables of organizational innovation with indicator dimensions of new ideas, creativity and responsiveness, the existence of new products and services, new ways of handling a program. This means that organizational innovation is not caused by these four dimensions. These results do not coincide with the results of Sartika's research (Sartika, 2015). Organizational innovation has a positive effect on organizational performance. Research that product innovation has a positive effect on customer loyalty Sinurat et al. (Sinurat et al., 2017), This result is different from the results of Prihartini & Sanusi's research (Prihartini & Sanusi, 2019) organizational innovation has no significant effect on MSME performance. This is in accordance with the General Guidelines for the Implementation of Higher Education Innovation Management (Directorate of Innovation Systems Kemenristekdikti, 2018) organizational innovation has an effect on improving company performance. Dama & Ogi (Dama & Ogi, 2018), Sulistyani & Lathifah (Sulistyani & Lathifah, 2020) Positive innovation affects organizational performance.

(iv) Organizational innovation variable on service image. Which is positively related to the service image in terms of the dimensions of new ideas, creativity and responsiveness, the existence of new products and services, new ways of handling a program. These results are in line with the results of Putra & Ekawati's research (Putra & Ekawati, 2017), Sinurat et al. (Sinurat et al., 2017), This research shows that product innovation has a significant effect on customer loyalty. Research that product innovation has a positive effect on Ukhwah customer loyalty (Ukhwah, 2019). This coincides with research Ainun (Ainun, 2020), Ali et al (Ali et al., 2015) product innovation affects customer loyalty.

5. Conclusion

According to the results of the study, it can be **concluded** as follows:

- 1.(i) Organizational performance is influenced by service leadership. The dimensions of organizational performance indicators are: financial sector, customer satisfaction improvement, process efficiency change, policy change innovation towards service system. (ii) Service image is not influenced by service leadership variable with indicator dimensions: good or bad impression from the consumer, consumer trust becomes loyalty, customer perception attitude that makes a good or bad image. (iii). Organizational innovation affects organizational performance with indicator dimensions of new ideas, creativity and responsiveness, new products and services, new ways of handling a program (iv) Service image is influenced by organizational innovation variables on the organization in terms of indicator dimensions measured by three impressions good or bad from the consumer, consumer trust becomes loyalty, the attitude of the customer perception that creates a good or bad image
2. **In terms of the contribution of receipts to the development of science:** An application of a good theory may not necessarily be carried out according to the original theory, for the Indonesian situation it should be adjusted to local conditions and situations.
3. **Submission of receipt limitations**
 - (i) This study has several limitations, the result of a research luck is that from some respondents there are agencies that subtly return to become respondents, so there are limitations to the respondents studied. Measurement of data using a questionnaire whose accuracy of answers really depends on each other's opinions & / the willingness and ability of the respondents, which is sometimes less cooperative by the agency as the object of research in terms of researchers getting information about the data they have, so that research results cannot be published more optimally in order to improve organizational performance and employee development & training. (ii) Limitations in generalizing the data, this research is in accordance with existing variables or in accordance with existing objects. (iii) Collecting data using a questionnaire whose accuracy of answers depends on the opinion of each and the willingness and ability of the respondents, in addition to the questionnaire the use of questionnaires, the participation of respondents is rather low. The combination of a filled-in questionnaire with an interview will result in a higher level of answer accuracy, although this method takes a longer time.
4. **Suggestions for further researchers** . In order to obtain significant results, a good theory may not necessarily be applicable in Indonesian conditions. For further researchers, quantitative and qualitative methods can be carried out to research with different variables or different locations and the instrument is not only in the form of questionnaires, but also direct interviews with the sources, so that the expected results are more perfect.

Construct Validity and Reliability

Test Validity test with reference to AVE value 0.5

Construct Reliability with reference Reliability 0.7

			Standardized Loading	Measurement Error	AVE	Reliability
ORGAPER	<---	SERLEAD	0.181	0.114	1,00011	1,000
SERIMA	<---	SERLEAD	0.016	0.084	0.520	0.781
SERIMA	<---	INNOCA	0.164	0.082	0.523	0.785

- All AVE values 0.5, so all constructs have valid.
- All reliability values 0.7, so all constructs are reliable.

▪ Goodness of Fit (GOF) Index	Cut Value	Off	Model Test Results	Information
Chi Square	Small		465.283	Small (Good)
Probability	0.05		.000	Good
CMIN/DF	2.00		1.923	Good
TLI	0.95		.203	Good
CFI	0.95		.301	Good
RMSEA	0.080		.080	Good

Model Feasibility Requirements:

Small Expected Chi Square

Probability 0.05

CMIN/DF 2.00

RMSEA 0.08

TLI 0.95

CFI 0.95

Results meet the requirements

Standardized Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			estimate
ORGANIZATION PERFORMANCE	<---	INNOVATION ABILITY	.233
PERFORMANCE ORGANIZATION	<---	Servant Leadership	-.616
SERVICE IMAGE	<---	INNOVATION ABILITY	-.950
SERVICE IMAGE	<---	Servant Leadership	.216
SERVICE IMAGE	<---	ORGANIZATION PERFORMANCE	.121

MODEL SEM-PLS END OF

Reference

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